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Housing crisis in European cities: exploring the potential of social and collaborative housing for supporting newcomers

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ABSTRACT

Contemporary global migration is increasingly driven by violence, conflict and climate change-related disasters. A decade ago, the 2015 refugee crisis sparked public and academic debate on arrival structures for newcomers. For those who reach EU territories, the urgent need for housing remains acute, shaped by discriminatory policies, Europe's deepening housing crisis and a pervasive perception of affordable housing scarcity.

This paper investigates how collective housing systems create multicultural urban spaces in European cities. Through an analysis of social and collaborative housing projects in Barcelona and Vienna, our research identifies key factors to enhance the social and spatial integration of newcomers.

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Introduction

The number of individuals and families displaced by disaster and conflict continuously grows. In that regard, the UNHCR reported the concerning amount of 122.6 million worldwide, with 72.1 million internally displaced persons (IDPs) and 32 million under refugee protection status (UNHCR 2024). Despite the number of displaced people doubling in the last ten years (UNHCR 2012), humanitarian assistance budgets have only experienced a marginal increase (Development Initiatives 2023) and remain insufficient to meet people's needs.

Due to upward migration trends, the imperative for arrival cities (Wilson 2022) to develop humane integration policies and housing facilities for newcomers is of paramount importance. However, worldwide as well as in Europe, which is our focus in this paper, governments not only fail to provide appropriate housing but also continue to enforce stringent regulations on asylum-seeking procedures and border controls, leaving many displaced persons in limbo and vulnerable to exploitation (MSF 2023). And even though the so-called 'refugee crisis' of 2015 (Bojadžijev and Mezzadra 2015) has promptly drawn greater attention to the way asylum seekers are being treated within the European Union (Kron and Lebuhn 2020; Özdemir 2022; Vandevordt and Verschraegen 2019) high rejection rates persist in all European countries (Sturge 2022).

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In the backdrop of Europe's worsening housing crisis, the issue of affordable and suitable housing is a major issue for the majority of the population (Housing Europe 2023). Over the last decade, access to housing has become a scarce resource in Europe driven by the increasing privatization, financialization, and speculation within the housing sector, coupled with reduced subsidies for social housing (Czischke and van Bortel 2018; Ronald 2013). While social and collective housing models aim to counter rising rents, they face substantial pressure from the free market.

The concept of 'affordable housing' has emerged as a response to the shortage of adequate housing and changes in social housing stock across many European countries (Czischke and van Bortel 2018). A notable trend in recent years has been the rise of collaborative housing initiatives led by housing providers and self-managed resident groups (Fromm 2012; International Collaborative Housing Conference Stockholm and; Vestbro 2010). These initiatives prioritise sustainability, community-centred, self-organised ways of living with high resident involvement (Czischke, Carriou, and Lang 2020). However, it remains unclear whether these social and collective housing markets are accessible to refugees. A renowned example is Vienna, where a significant portion of the population resides in subsidised social housing apartments (Hözl 2021; Kazepov and Verwiebe 2021). Contrary to the simplistic assumption of easy access to the housing system, research has revealed that refugees face substantial barriers to entering the social housing market during their initial years of residence, owing to the stringent bureaucratic allocation procedures enforced by the city council (Aigner 2019; Kohlbacher 2020).

Our aim in this paper is to examine the potential of social and collaborative housing to facilitate the integration of refugees into European cities. Thereby, we refrain from the traditional, one-sided notion of integration and instead refer to the concept of convivial disintegration whenever we speak about integration (Meissner and Heil 2021).

We specifically focus on collective forms of housing because they typically accommodate more robust tenant communities than conventional housing on the free market. Additionally, within the context of neoliberal urbanism (Apostolopoulou and Liodaki 2021; Peck, Theodore, and Brenner 2013), it can offer a more affordable/financially accessible option for displaced persons who are grappling with financial and social challenges as a result of their often involuntary displacement.

Newcomers co-creating multicultural urban spaces in Europe and beyond

In the following sections, where we elaborate on the broader context to situate our research and our theoretical framework, we use the term 'newcomers' to collectively refer to asylum seekers, refugees and migrants arriving in a 'Western city' of the Global North (Kaika and Keith 2021). Before addressing the issue of housing, it is essential to emphasize that current EU governmental policies, systematic prevention practices at the EU's external borders, and routinely deployed illegal tactics by state authorities, such as 'pushbacks' (Davies, Isakjee, and Obradovic-Wochnik 2023), violate fundamental rights (many cases of injustices are brought to light by international organisations such as Human Rights Watch and Amnesty International (Amnesty International 2023b; Human Rights Watch 2023)). These practices aim to forcefully expel asylum seekers from EU territory leaving refugees vulnerable to traffickers and, tragically, resulting in

loss of life in the Mediterranean Sea (Gaitanou 2023). EU's externalization and militarization policies seek to stop people outside its borders at all costs so that they cannot even apply for asylum, violating the Geneva Convention and a fundamental human right (Convention Relating to the Status of Refugees 1951; United Nations 1948). Here, we do not analyse the widely-covered impacts of anti-migration policies in European countries (Amnesty International 2023a; Kuiper 2023; Marsh and Rinke 2023; J. Wilson and Brito 2023); instead, we focus on what occurs after refugees have managed to reach a European country. Nonetheless, we assert the paramount importance of understanding the violence and hardships imposed on refugees and newcomers and the necessity of finding ways to integrate them into the societies they have managed to reach.

EU member states coordinate refugee flows through the Common European Asylum System, which theoretically ensures the maintenance of specific standards regarding asylum and reception procedures. The primary treaty delineating rights for forcibly displaced individuals, who are classified as refugees and thus protected under international law, is the 1951 UN Convention relating to the status of refugees (Brown, Gill, and Halsall 2022; Convention Relating to the Status of Refugees 1951). This convention includes provisions for the right to housing but also its social and cultural dimensions, such as the ability to maintain community connections and preserve cultural identity, as articulated in documents such as the 1948 Universal Declaration of Human Rights (United Nations 1948) and the 1966 International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (UN General Assembly 1966).

While these legal frameworks do exist, refugees and asylum seekers, in reality, encounter profound challenges and a lack of support when attempting to access housing, all within the backdrop of a hostile environment in neoliberal contexts. Concerning the management of housing for refugees, certain neoliberal policy trends within welfare states, marked by state withdrawal and increased privatization, have led to the financialization of this housing sector (Kreichauf 2018). Several scholars (Darling 2016; Hill, Meer, and Peace 2021; Meer et al. 2021) have documented a decline in the value and quality of accommodations for asylum seekers, particularly within initial reception centres. These centres, which often embody spatial segregation and racial discrimination, exhibit variations in spatial configuration, organisation and duration of stay based on location and the policies of national governments (Dadusc, Grazioli, and Martínez 2019). Poor living conditions found in reception centres and other 'short-term' (often longer-term) accommodations have been empirically linked to adverse effects on the mental health of asylum seekers, their capacity to integrate, and their ability to (re)establish their livelihoods, contributing significantly to social inequalities in societies (Brown, Gill, and Halsall 2022).

In this paper, we view newcomers as active agents who enrich urban life through their cultural contributions, labour, and everyday practices. In doing so, they co-create the city and challenge its rigid spatial configurations, historically shaped by capital accumulation and colonial legacies. We understand cities as multicultural and contested urban geographies but also as sites of hope for refugees – spaces that prompt political engagement within host societies to reconsider notions of mutual obligations, shared futures and the imperatives of hospitality (Kaika and Keith 2021). By framing newcomers as co-creators of the city, we draw on Lefebvre's (1992) influential theory of the social production of space, which adopts an inclusive perspective and suggests that every city dweller –

regardless of citizenship status – participates in the socio-spatial (re)production of urban life (Lefebvre 1992; see also Apostolopoulou and Liodaki 2021, 2025).

Paradoxically, contemporary nationalism often excludes ethnic and cultural ‘others’ preventing disadvantaged groups from fully participating in this social production and from shaping the city (Purcell 2003). This exclusion contrast sharply with historical examples of multiethnic cities. For instance, 15th and 16th century Venice flourished as a bustling hub of Mediterranean trade, attracting and integrating a diverse multicultural community (Petkov 2020). In central Europe, the Austro-Hungarian Empire (1867–1918) stands out as an example of a multicultural landscape, where free movement across the entire territory enabled the emergence of multiethnic hubs that influenced education, culture, leisure, emancipation and trade (Horel 2023). Although the Austro-Hungarian Empire contested multicultural spaces in the beginning, the ‘*Vielvölkerstaat*’ (multiethnic state) gradually pushed political agency for all male citizens and rights to education for all. Similarly, New York, founded in the 17th century, became a magnet for large waves of European immigrants in the late 19th and early 20th centuries (Foner 2014), later welcoming African Americans after World War I and Puerto Ricans after the World War II, with migration continuing to diversify the city (Foner 2007) despite the major challenges due to reactionary migration policies. Political theorist Hannah Arendt, for example, experienced that US immigration centres often viewed arriving immigrants from war-torn Europe as hostile foreigners instead of future citizens (Hannah 1943). All of these multiethnic landscapes were contested, but at their core, multicultural, granting the right to socially co-produce the city to all their citizens.

Despite this rich history of multicultural urbanism, today’s restrictive entry policies block many from seeking refuge in cities. Structural inequalities have, *inter alia*, transformed Europe into an increasingly inaccessible destination for displaced individuals and families (Costello and Mann 2020; Davies, Isakjee, and Obradovic-Wochnik 2023; Van Houtum and Pijpers 2007). The promise of emerging multicultural urban spaces ‘where people can come to terms with ethnic difference and where the voicing of racism can be muted’ (Amin 2002, 967) is therefore under threat. Within this context, municipalities play a pivotal role in driving social and political change by facilitating newcomers’ rights, including the granting of visas, residency and refugee status. Rather than ignoring the presence of refugees and displaced persons, municipalities must acknowledge their existence and advocate for their rights (Roth and Russel 2018).

Refugee integration through social and collaborative housing

In what follows, we specifically focus on refugee integration through alternative housing, a topic for which both research and practical implementation remain limited. We start from the assumption/hypothesis that social and collaborative housing represent potentially efficient alternatives for refugee integration since they predominantly exist outside the profit-driven, capitalist free market for housing provision and are often supported by communities and grassroots groups.

While the social and affordable housing market is indeed under pressure to offer below-market rents and meet the rising demand for housing (Housing Europe 2023), it has also undergone significant structural transformations in several European countries. These changes have been driven by austerity measures following the global economic

crisis of 2008 (Apostolopoulou and Adams 2015), a policy shift toward promoting homeownership and private rental markets through privatisation and the increasing diversification of the housing sector itself (Czischke and van Bortel 2018). As neoliberal agendas have taken hold across much of Europe, the social housing stock has declined markedly. Rather than expanding public housing, governments have increasingly focused on regulating the existing stock, leading to long waiting lists (European Action Coalition 2021). Both housing movements and scholars have strongly criticised governments' failure to counter the commodification and financialization of the housing sector (García-Lamarca and Kaika 2016; Priemus and Dieleman 2002; Scanlon, Whitehead, and Fernandez Arrigoitia 2014; Soederberg 2018).

Within this context of weak social housing systems, affordable housing has also become a scarce resource, turning housing into a highly debated issue across Europe. Until 2024, the EU has delegated the issue of affordable housing to its member states. The recent establishment of a 'Special Committee on the Housing Crisis' by the European Parliament, working with the Commission to create an 'Affordable Housing Plan', offers hope for European-wide action (European Parliament 2025). In 2021, European citizens spent 19% of their disposable income on housing, with particularly vulnerable individuals facing an even greater burden, spending 38% of their income (Eurostat 2023). The prevailing institutional understanding of 'affordable housing' is that it offers rents below market rates and serves a broader range of vulnerable people compared to the social housing sector (Oxley & Smith 1996) (Figure 1). Therefore, it can be seen as a crucial bridge between the social and the fully market-oriented rental sectors, accommodating tenants who are ineligible for social housing but cannot afford market rents, which are exacerbated by supply and demand dynamics (Czischke and van Bortel 2018).

On the other hand, the term 'collaborative housing' is used to encompass a variety of self-managed housing concepts rooted in collective tenant solidarity (Fromm 2012). Collaborative housing operates outside market-oriented principles and centres around people's needs (Tummers 2015). Within this realm, alongside cooperatives, collaborative housing extends from community-led and participatory co-housing to self-build movements and other ecological and social housing initiatives. Housing concepts vary depending on participants' values, the socioeconomic and legal context, and historical precedents (Thompson 2020). Through participatory design practises, prospective

Figure 1. Rental housing segments, adapted from Czischke and van Bortel (2018).

residents have the opportunity to shape both the physical spaces of their individual dwellings and shared common areas (Fromm 2012). In Austria this core group of residents is called *Baugruppe*. Many recent collaborative projects in Europe have emerged since the 1990s in response to the challenges posed by post-recession and austerity policies, driven by a collective desire to establish affordable housing (Vestbro 2010). This collaborative effort, uniting residents' assemblies with traditional housing providers, aims to address the persisting housing crises in our societies. This becomes essential since housing production and provision by governments, the free market and the third sector have mostly fallen short in addressing structural crises (Czischke 2018).

Housing scholars Czischke and Huisman (2018) contend that collaborative housing models can be effective and innovative tools for fostering the integration of refugees. Their research on the Dutch pilot project 'Startblok' in Amsterdam illustrates this, highlighting how the initiative addresses both the shortage of affordable housing in the Netherlands and provides alternative housing opportunities for young Dutch adults and young refugees. We would also like to highlight the important work of Arroyo, Montesino, Johansson and Wasim Yahia on the Sweden collaborative housing project 'SällBo', which focuses on the socio-spatial dimensions of integration within a diverse residential community (Arroyo et al. 2021). Like Czischke and Huisman (2018), they apply Ager and Strang's (2008) integration framework to explore the social connections among elderly residents, young Swedes and young refugees who live there and share common spaces.

Despite these important contributions, research on inclusive communities within collaborative housing models remains limited. Brown, Gill, and Halsall (2022) in their literature review on the impact of housing on refugees, aimed to contribute to broader effort to challenge the structural inequalities constraining refugees' lives. They found that conditions in reception facilities for refugees and migrants were often poor, posing significant risks to physical and mental health and promoting social segregation and discrimination within host societies.

Similarly to Brown, Gill, and Halsall (2022), we advocate for a significantly reduced stay in such centres, followed by a long-term, successful integration into non-segregated, non-stigmatized housing. Despite emerging studies and ongoing concerns about the housing conditions faced by newcomers -refugees and unwanted migrants- there is currently no supra-national legal framework established by the EU for the reception, shelter, and integration of forcibly displaced individuals. The full responsibility for these matters rests with the receiving member states (Whelan n.d.).

Understanding integration and belonging to a new place

Housing is commonly recognized as a pivotal determinant of (un)successful integration (Ager and Strang 2008). Nevertheless, the precise nexus between housing and integration remains a relatively underexplored area of research. Existing academic literature has primarily focused on housing accessibility rather than delving into the quality of the built environment and its specific ramifications for refugees (Brown, Gill, and Halsall 2022).

While the concept of integration is highly individualised and context-dependent, Ager and Strang (2008) have formulated a normative framework, which comprises four

key factors as ‘potential means to support the achievement of integration’: employment, housing, education, and health (169) (Figure 2). Regarding housing, the Dutch Refugee Council/ECRE (2001, 5) poignantly captures the predicament faced by refugees: ‘The difference between a house and a home is the difference between a place to stay and a place to live. A home is a place of safety, security and stability, the lack of which was the main reason refugees left their country of origin’. This framework is grounded on refugees’ ‘citizenship and rights’ and is constructed in a multidimensional manner, with a central focus on two primary mediating factors: facilitators and social connections (Phillimore 2020). The latter is crucial in fostering refugees’ sense of belonging in their new environment and can be categorised as ‘social bonds (with family and co-ethnic, co-national, co-religious, or other forms of groups), social bridges (with other communities), and social links (with the structures of the state)’ (Ager and Strang 2008, 178).

The integration process is inherently dynamic, involving reciprocal adjustments between migrants and the receiving society (Czischke and Huisman 2018). In contrast, ‘assimilation’ refers to a one-sided endeavour in which refugees seek to adapt culturally to the host community (Strang, Baillot, and Mignard 2017). Early on, Berry (1997) argues that alternative futures marked by cultural diversity become possible when there is a shared commitment to flexibly transform established relationships. Refugees embark on this integration process from a disadvantaged position, often emerging from traumatic circumstances that forced them to leave their home country. Additionally, they may have limited familiarity with culture-specific practices, which can pose challenges in obtaining recognition for their educational and professional qualifications acquired in their country of origin (Berry 1997). Even before the so-called ‘refugee crisis’ in 2015 Hall (2013) suggested, that Western welfare states should invest in a plural democracy, empowering newcomers to participate and establishing accessibility to core integration means (Ager and Strang 2008). Amin

Figure 2. A conceptual framework defining core domains of integration, adapted from Ager and Strang (2008).

profoundly coined the term ‘conviviality’, which describes lived multiculturalism in an environment of ‘thrown togetherness’ (Massey 2005), where strangers do not have any pre-existing social ties. The concept of conviviality directly relates ‘to community cohesion, local cultural legacy or shared sense of place’ (Amin 2010). In our case-study research, we analyse everyday conviviality among non-intentional (Barcelona examples) and intentional (Viennese examples) communities of diverse, multicultural residents.

Building upon Ager and Strang’s framework, Korac (2003) explored that constructing ‘bridging social capital’ is the most highly regarded integration tool among newcomers, with particular emphasis on fostering social connections with the host community. This underscores the potential of social and collaborative housing as typologies that enable meaningful social interaction and accelerate integration processes due to their strong focus on community-centred principles. Furthermore, it is important to note that alliances between newcomers and citizens can also extend beyond the housing context to other communal spaces within the city (Nagi et al. 2023). These spaces play a pivotal role in nurturing a sense of belonging through community-led, inclusive initiatives.

Belonging has been widely researched in relation to migrants’ experiences in new environments (Amit and Bar-Lev 2015; Dromgold-Sermen 2022; Liu, Zhang, and Wu 2022) as well as refugee’s experiences (Anthias 2006; Fuchs et al. 2021; Saygı 2023). Yuval-Davis (2006) identifies three distinct dimensions to the sense of belonging: firstly, belonging rooted in shared social identities such as gender, class, ethnicity and nationality; secondly, belonging shaped by personal identifications and emotional attachments, often framed through narratives of ‘us’ and ‘them’; and thirdly, belonging grounded in shared ethical and political values. Migrants and refugees occupy a unique position in the realm of belonging, as their sense of belonging is frequently challenged and disrupted during resettlement (Yuval-Davis 2006). They navigate the emerging complexities of belonging by grappling with severed ties to their original homes while simultaneously forging new connections in their refuge destinations (Anthias 2006). Living communities that foster ‘bridging social capital’ can help (re-)build a sense of belonging. Residents, especially in collaborative housing, often report a strong sense of attachment to their housing, which in turn strengthens the community’s social cohesion (Lang 2019). This stands in contrast to anonymous housing arrangements in the private rental market, where residents rarely know their neighbours.

At a spatial level, the underexplored concept of place-belongingness helps illuminate how newcomers integrate into new environments. Place-belongingness refers to an emotional attachment to a place, where one feels comfort, security and familiarity. It is a socially constructed experience shaped by memories and everyday interactions. This sense of place-belongingness can manifest across various spatial scales, from the home to the urban commons and even the nation-state (Lähdesmäki et al. 2016). Furthermore, it is intricately linked to autobiographical, relational, cultural, economic, and legal factors (Antonsich 2010).

By focusing specifically on the integration pillar of housing, we emphasise the spatial dimension through the lens of place-belongingness. To situate this concept, it is useful to briefly revisit the idea of the social production of space. De Certeau’s classic work *The Practice of Everyday Life* (de Certeau 1988) draws

a critical distinction between *place* (*lieu*) from *space* (*espace*), arguing that space is a product of social practices and relations that unfold within a specific place – ‘the street geometrically defined by urban planning is transformed into a space by walkers’ (de Certeau 1988, 117). Building on this, Lefebvre (1991) delves deeper into the concept of space, conceptualising it as encompassing not only the perception of everyday spatial practices but also the symbolic representations and lived experiences generated through social encounters. In the communities we study, daily social interactions help cultivate a sense of belonging, transforming communal *places* into meaningful *spaces* that foster place-belongingness. Hence, convivial everyday life facilitates the appropriation of spaces and nurtures attachment to the built environment (Fenster 2004).

Methodology and case studies

Practices of inclusive and multicultural living communities: empirical evidence from Vienna and Barcelona

We conducted research in two EU cities with distinct housing histories: Vienna, the capital of Austria, and Barcelona, the capital city of Catalonia, Spain. Specifically, we analysed three examples of inclusive, collaborative housing in Vienna, where the collaborative housing sector is currently experiencing a revival (Lang 2019). Starting with a project from the 1990s – *Sargfabrik* – we then examined two more recent projects by the architecture office *einszuseinsarchitektur*: *OASE.inklusiv* (completed in 2021) and *Gleis 21* (completed in 2019) (Map 1). In Barcelona, where the collaborative housing sector is only slowly emerging with a few notable examples such as *La Borda* (Brysch, Mateu, and Czischke 2024), we instead focused on two historical cases of multicultural co-living in the social housing sector: *Case Bloc* and *Bellvitge* (Map 2).

Map 1. Map of Vienna showing the three CH projects: Sargfabrik, Gleis 21 & OASE.Inklusiv, self-derived (2025).

Map 2. Map of Barcelona showing the two social housing projects: Casa Bloc & Bellvitge, self-derived (2025).

Later in this chapter, we will introduce the specific Austrian and Spanish context of migration trends.

We applied a mixed-method approach to conduct an in-depth analysis of inclusive living arrangements. Our methodology is anchored in the theoretical intersections of architecture and urban studies, human geography, migration and housing studies. Empirically, we combined qualitative social science methods (Knott et al. 2022; Roulston, deMarrais, and Lewis 2003) with architectural research techniques (Niezabitowska 2018). The latter included producing photo series, maps such as floor plans and sections to identify spaces of social encounter, as well as a photo challenge with one newcomer living in *Gleis 21*. High-quality spatial elements that foster everyday conviviality were determined by ethnographic observation (site visits that lasted for the course of one day) – how residents use and appropriate spaces – and derived from personal conversation, when residents reflected on their spatial relations.

During fieldwork, which included at least two site visits to each housing project, we conducted semi-structured interviews and ad-hoc conversations with residents and newcomers living in the complexes. Whenever residents had more time, we interviewed them with their consent, rather than just having an ad-hoc conversation. This was crucial to gain deeper insights into their inclusive everyday life. Additionally, we engaged with various stakeholders involved in the Viennese projects, including the architectural office *einzieinsarchitektur*, an expert from *wohnbund:consult*, the manager of the refugee services NGO *Diakonie Flüchtlingsdienst* (semi-structured interviews) as well as the barista in the Café at *Gleis 21* and staff at *Sarfabrik's* restaurant (ad-hoc conversations). These exchanges took place in April and May 2023 and again in April and May 2024. The conversations with Austrian residents were held in German, transcribed and translated by the author Birkner.

In the Barcelona context, we also applied architectural research techniques, which helped us to analyse plans and drawings and to create photo series from both sites. For the social analysis, we conducted ad-hoc conversations and semi-structured interviews (when participants had more time) with Spanish residents, newly arrived refugees and newcomers who have been living in both complexes for a while now. Our fieldwork took place in May 2023. The conversations with Spanish citizens were conducted by the authors in Spanish as well as transcribed and translated. We were unfortunately restrained from holding stakeholder interviews due to the low response rate of contacted actors in the field of (refugee) housing.

From our conversations, we draw the most valuable insights relevant to this paper's focus on inclusive communities and the built environment, and connect them with our theoretical framework and our learnings from the literature.

Vienna's multicultural history and its refugee housing sector

In Vienna, a 2009 municipal policy embedding 'social sustainability' criteria in building competitions has helped foster inclusive communities in the collaborative housing sector over the past decade (Birkner 2024; Lang 2019). As a result, *Gleis 21* and *OASE.inklusiv* were realised under favourable conditions, including access to land, subsidies, and early cooperation with refugee housing actors (Birkner 2024). Historically, Austria has a long tradition of multiculturalism, spanning internal

migration during the Habsburg Monarchy, post-World War II refugee movements and structured labour migration from Spain, Turkey and Yugoslavia (Rupnow 2017). Austria also experienced a substantial influx of newcomers in 2015, surpassing the levels seen in many other European Union nations, with a total of 88,340 individuals applying for refugee status. However, once international protection is secured, newcomers face a challenging housing market with limited access to social or affordable housing (Kohlbacher 2020). Vienna has emerged as the primary destination for newcomers and consistently extends support even to ‘non-removed rejected asylum seekers’ (Ataç, Schütze, and Reitter 2020).

We next outline current strategies in the Viennese refugee (housing) sector and explain why these practices incorporate progressive and innovative aspects. Until recently, newcomers were allocated flats for six months as part of basic welfare support (*Grundversorgung*) (UNHCR Austria 2024), after which they were largely pushed onto the private market for up to three years, facing high rents and substandard conditions before becoming eligible for social housing. More recently, the municipality of Vienna, together with the Austrian umbrella organisation of homelessness service providers (BAWO) has begun implementing the ‘housing first approach’, aiming to make affordable housing accessible to vulnerable groups, including newcomers and homeless persons (BAWO 2017). This shift has launched multi-sector collaborations between the municipality (main donor), refugee service NGOs, housing providers and resident communities.

Today, Vienna’s refugee housing sector operates across three main channels: i) social housing; ii) cooperative and collaborative housing; and iii) the private market (Birkner 2024). NGOs typically provide transitional housing for two to three years, holding the rental agreement and securing temporary rights for newcomers. In the social housing sector, municipal property management *Wiener Wohnen* allocates flats to NGOs; in the cooperative sector, cooperatives and collaborative housing communities, reserve a certain amount of apartments within their complexes for social use; and in the private sector, opportunities arise through refurbishment projects.

These strategies aim to secure dignified, affordable housing for newcomers during their first three years following the initial six months of basic welfare support. Collaborative housing projects, motivated by solidary and social criteria embedded in the *building competition* (*Bauträgerwettbewerb*) (Azevedo et al. 2023; Reven-Holzmann 2019), offer more flexible and individualised housing solutions compared to the rigid social housing system, the expensive cooperative system with high entry fees, or the tight and unaffordable private market. Typically, the refugee NGO holds the lease with the housing collective for around three years, after which both parties may transfer the apartment directly to the newcomer, if desired (Zeitlinger 2024).

Barcelona’s efforts to receive newcomers amidst a strained housing system

In Barcelona, we selected two social housing examples -Casa Bloc and Bellvitge- to assess the theoretical and practical potential of multicultural co-living embedded in these housing models. Barcelona’s migration history offers a unique context: under Francoist dictatorship (until 1975), no immigration laws existed and Spain did not

admit newcomers (Garcés Mascareñas and Moreno Amador 2019). While Spain had only a 1% foreign-born population in 1990, this figure surged to 12.2% by 2010 (Hansen 2019). Although Spain ratified the 1951 Geneva Refugee Convention after Franco's regime, nearly half of asylum seekers were not granted entry, and rejection rates reached about 70% in subsequent years (Garcés Mascareñas and Moreno Amador 2019). Like other European countries, the refugee crisis of 2015 marked a significant shift: Barcelona began receiving hundreds to thousands of newcomers annually, with the entire country processing 65,404 asylum applications in 2021 and a rejection rate of 71.2% (Asylum Information Database 2021; Hansen 2019). Before the so-called refugee crisis, the reception system was centrally managed, with Madrid wielding ultimate decision-making authority. In recent years, the city of Barcelona, drawing on its rich history of solidarity movements, has initiated proactive welcoming initiatives such as 'Barcelona Ciutat Refugi' ('Barcelona Refugee City') and 'Casa Nostra, Casa Vostra' ('Our Home, Your Home') (Agustín and Jørgensen 2019; Hansen 2019).

Up until 2018, the Spanish reception system operated in three distinct phases. In the first, the reception phase, newcomers were assigned to live in centres and facilities managed by the governments or NGOS (wherever places were available) for a period of up to six, and at most nine, months (De Gasperis et al. 2016–2021). During this stage, individuals received shelter assistance to cover basic needs as well as access to trauma support and introductory cultural integration courses. The second, integration phase, lasted up to six, maximum of eleven months and provided individuals and families with financial assistance to help them independently secure rental housing. Given the major challenges of accessing the housing market, support by COSs (civil society organisations) was established. Finally, the autonomy phase offered limited additional assistance for another four to six months. A key problem, however, has been the Spanish's stated misguided assumption that asylum seekers can achieve full 'autonomy' within Spanish society during this period, effectively placing the responsibility for finding work and housing on the individuals themselves (Garcés Mascareñas and Moreno Amador 2019).

Simultaneously, newcomers in Spain find themselves amidst a housing crisis worsened by the 2008 financial crisis and further exacerbated by the chronic shortage of social and affordable housing. This dire situation has forced many to live in substandard, overcrowded conditions or even on the streets (Garcés-Mascareñas 2014; Hansen 2019). Despite the existence of various social movements, the city persistently fails to provide adequate housing for all its residents, with the increasing number of evictions becoming a distressing norm (Ribbons 2023).

Against this backdrop, we sought to explore new housing possibilities for arriving refugees in Barcelona. We identified factors that enhance conviviality within each project, with a particular focus on common spaces. Moreover, we conducted informal ad-hoc interviews and conversations with several residents, including refugees, to gauge their perspectives on the realities and potential of co-living with refugee families. We captured the residents' opinions and willingness to embrace newcomers as part of their 'host community'. As already mentioned, we also analysed the common spaces using photography and architectural drawings.

Findings and discussion

Collaborative housing in Vienna: social bridging in Sargfabrik, OASE.Inklusiv and Gleis 21

In all three case studies, we found that social bonding occurred through everyday interactions among neighbours sharing demographic, socio-economic or ethnic backgrounds. Bridging emerged through connections between newcomers and the existing community, often facilitated by buddy or mentor networks that supported newcomers from the moment they move in. Linking capital was strengthened through partnerships with NGOs or other organisations that allocated apartments or provided additional support.

Our findings align with our key learnings from the literature. Thus, we can apply concepts of social cohesion and inclusion in collaborative, inclusive communities to our examined housing complexes (Williams 2005). While social cohesion typically relies on bonding social capital, social inclusion is amplified through bridging social capital (Putnam 2000). Bonding refers to interaction within relatively homogeneous groups, whereas bridging spans diverse, multicultural groups (Poortinga 2012). A third dimension, linking social capital, describes relationships with institutional stakeholders (Agger and Jensen 2015; Lang and Novy 2011).

All three *Baugruppen* (*Sargfabrik*, *OASE.inklusiv* & *Gleis 21*) deliberately chose to welcome newcomers. We asked members when and how they decided to create inclusive and solidarity-based co-living communities. In a semi-structured interview conducted in the living room of a resident in *Sargfabrik*, it was shared that the so-called *Flexwohnungen* were part of the *Sargfabrik's* concept from the outset:

When we decided to initiate this huge co-living project, we also wanted to provide housing units to those who could least afford it. (Resident from *Sargfabrik*, semi-structured interview, April 22, 2024)

These units, scattered throughout the *Sargfabrik* complex, are financed through a solidarity model whereby the entire community pushes the rents down by paying slightly more. Contrary to regular *Baugruppen* members, tenants of *Flexwohnungen* pay only a subsidised monthly rent without an entry fee. In 2015, the year of the refugee crisis with a sudden influx of newcomers in Vienna, *Sargfabrik* offered *Flexwohnungen* to NGOs working in the migration sector and launched a mentorship programme to connect refugee families to the community. While some families later moved on to other housing, others remained, finding the co-living environment in *Sargfabrik* well-suited to their needs. A resident reflected:

It is interesting that while we were very responsive to the 2015 refugee wave, we did not feel the same urgency during the wave of Ukrainian refugees. We felt that the solidarity system among Austrians to support Ukrainians was much stronger than it had been for refugees and migrants from the Middle East in 2015. (Resident from *Sargfabrik*, semi-structured interview, April 22, 2024)

The *OASE.inklusiv* project was initially planned with the property developer *Neues Leben*, the consultancy *wohnbund:consult* and the NGO *Neunerimmo* (Einszueins 2023). The research project *MICOLL* (stands for Migrants in Collaborative Housing)

accompanied and studied this participatory design process. Although newcomers were included in the process, many dropped out due to pressing housing needs and limited time resources (Kain et al. 2023). An employer of *wohnbund:consult* emphasized that refugees are not a homogeneous group, as each person has individual needs and finds support networks in different ways. Similarly, each person has a unique need for community involvement. During our interview, he shared:

One possible solution to the challenges faced by refugees in finding housing and employment is to offer opportunities for participation and active engagement within the community while ensuring that this is not mandatory for those who may prefer a more independent lifestyle. (Wohnbund:consult, semi-structured interview, May 12 2023)

In another interview, held with a member from *Gleis 21* in their apartment, we learned that the *Baugruppe* decided to design so-called *Soliwohnungen* (solidarity apartments) early on to fulfil the social sustainability criteria in the city councils' building competition, just like the *OASE.inklusive* Baugruppe (Azevedo et al. 2023; Reven-Holzmann 2019):

During the design phase, we decided to provide some apartments to vulnerable groups – in our case newcomers. We knew someone from NGO *Diakonie Flüchtlingsdienst* and initiated a collaboration. Our four *Soliwohnungen* are much smaller and cross-financed by tenants paying higher rent for bigger apartments. (Resident from Gleis 21, April 20, 2024)

At *Sargfabrik*, social bridging was actively fostered through a mentor system, with each newcomer assigned a specific community contact. Experiences varied: some residents required substantial support, while others needed little (Mentor from *Sargfabrik*, pers. comm.). Notably, some newcomers transitioned through *Sargfabrik* for two or three years, while others have settled in and moved within the complex to another apartment that fitted their needs. This possibility of moving within thanks to the larger scale of *Sargfabrik* is seen as a significant advantage by tenants and newcomers (Mentor from *Sargfabrik*, pers. comm.).

On the other side, *OASE.inklusive* faced major challenges in community building due to the COVID-19 pandemic coinciding with the moving-in period. The *Baugruppe* formed an active residents' association, which organised social events throughout. However, we found from a conversation with a member, that it was hard to get newcomers to participate, because they did not feel part of the initial group and pandemic restrictions hampered social interaction:

During the participatory design phase, we had the opportunity to build meaningful connections and foster a sense of community, a pivotal moment in my view. The everyday demand for community varies for each individual. Nevertheless, our commitment to promoting social gatherings, especially now in the post pandemic era, persists. (Resident from *OASE.inklusive*, semi-structured interview, May 2023)

Interestingly, the *Baugruppe* had not thought of a Mentor-Buddy initiative but instead tried to organise events to get to know each other. The process of community building to reach bridging social capital in an inclusive community requires time (Korac 2003). Everyday conviviality can only eventually lead to sense of belonging and place-

belongingness (Amin 2010; Yuval-Davis 2006; de Certeau 1988). A young man with a migration background shared in a conversation:

I am content here. The common spaces are interesting, but I think we need time to bring them to life. I know that a residents' association exists but I have not yet engaged - I am curious though. For my last birthday, I rented the multi-purpose room to celebrate with friends, that was wonderful. (Newcomer at OASE.inklusiv, semi-structured interview, May 2023)

The collaborative community *Gleis 21* started a *buddy-programme* to support social bridging between residents and newcomers living in four *Soliwohnungen*. According to a resident (from Gleis 21, 20 April 2024), all newcomers are well-integrated in the community though they cannot formally join the *Baugruppe* without moving to a regular apartment and paying the entry fee. The collaborative housing community has hosted, among others, a newcomer family with two adult sons (nationality not shared at the request of the research participant), a Ukrainian mother with two young children and an Afghan mother with a baby. While the refugee mothers occasionally struggled with precarious living conditions and childcare demands, they maintained connections through their buddies who proven to be a significant source of assistance, especially during challenging times, and have been instrumental in their social integration and settling into Vienna. The newcomer family, on the other hand, showed a high level of engagement and participation in the community. The parents have already moved on to another apartment in the social housing sector, but the two brothers still live in the complex (resident from Gleis 21, 20 April 2024). One brother expressed:

It feels like living in a huge family here and I like my small apartment. The communal spaces are great for social interaction and common activities and in my room I have privacy. It is definitely a very special place to live. (Newcomer from Gleis 21, May 1, 2024)

Social bridging (Ager and Strang 2008) is encouraged by the buddy program and as a buddy told us they are very flexible in adjusting to the newcomers' needs and do not apply a one-to-one system. Instead, newcomers are linked to the group and then naturally connect with the group's members on a personal level (Buddy from Gleis 21, 27 April 2024).

The *Baugruppe* drew a longer contract for the newcomer brothers and the Ukrainian woman with the NGO *Diakonie*. The buddy explained to us that this is one of the benefits of self-managed, collective housing (Buddy from Gleis 21, 27 April 2024): 'we always have space to discuss and change our trajectories.' This transit housing solution transformed into a longer-term option for newcomers.

Participatory design and appropriation of communal spaces

The collaborative housing model is fundamentally based on collective ownership and communal spaces. Future residents are involved in the design of individual and communal spaces through participatory methods (Czischke 2018). This enables architects to design according to residents' specific needs. After moving in, there is a higher

likelihood of inhabitants appropriating and caring for spaces as well as creating a sense of belonging (Anthias 2006; Yuval-Davis 2006) and place-belonging (Antonsich 2010; Lähdesmäki et al. 2016; Li 2024).

In recent years, the Viennese subsidised social housing system experienced a renewed emphasis on communal spaces particularly following the introduction of building competitions that incorporated social sustainability criteria in 2009 (Cucca and Friesenecker 2022; Schikowitz and Pohler 2024). The city of Vienna remains committed to subsidising high-quality community spaces within housing complexes, aiming to foster neighbourhood building and generate positive impacts on the broader society. These communal spaces are intended to accommodate a diverse range of users and include indoor, outdoor and transitional spaces (Wohnfonds Wien 2019).

Collective spaces within housing complexes are crucial for fostering everyday conviviality, enabling the appropriation of decommodified space, facilitating resource pooling and supporting shared care work (Gruber 2021). As such, collaborative housing offers an alternative to conventional housing models by explicitly providing commons. Through the practice of *commoning* (Kornberger and Borch 2015), which encompasses all collective activities related to communal spaces, residents appropriate and care for these spaces. This social production of space (Lefebvre 1992) when combined with spatial justice (Soja 2019) can be understood as a dynamic and evolving process, characterised by ongoing adaptation and change (Figure 3).

Figure 3 compares the communal spaces of selected collaborative housing projects. In the most established CH in Vienna, *Sargfabrik*, the residents find a range of communal spaces: roof terraces with landscape gardening, a swimming pool and sauna, a laundry room, outdoor gardens and playgrounds, a library and a community kitchen (Figure 4 and 5).

BRIEF COMPARISON OF COLLABORATIVE HOUSING PROJECTS: SARGFABRIK, GLEIS 21, OASE.INKLUSIV

	SARGFABRIK	GLEIS 21	OASE.INKLUSIV
Dimensions	extra-large: 112 units	large: 34 units	medium: 81 units
Legal Form	dormitory (Wohnheim)	dormitory (Wohnheim)	
Newcomers	Flexwohnungen: ca 20 refugees	4 Soliwohnungen: ca 7 refugees	10 - 15 refugees
Management	23 employees 	self-governing	self-governing
Public Social Spaces	event rooms (Kulturhaus), restaurant (Kant_in_e Vierzehn), kindergarten, swimmingpool and sauna 		
Semi-Public Social Spaces	roof terraces, swimming pool, laundry room, outdoor gardens and playgrounds, library, community kitchen 		
Communal Spaces of Social Encounter	exterior access staircases 		

Figure 3. A brief comparison of collaborative housing projects in Vienna, self-derived (2025).

Figure 4. Ground floor plans of Sargfabrik with spatial analysis, provided by BKK-3 architektur, adapted by the author (2024).

The housing project *Gleis 21* offers a community kitchen, a library, a retreat yoga room, a home-office space, an outside terrace, and urban gardening on its roof. In the cellar, one can encounter event rooms, a gym, a workshop, a community multi-purpose room and a laundry room (Figure 6). OASE.inklusiv is facilitated with multi-purpose room, a workshop, inner and outside playspaces, home-office, gardens and terraces (Figure 7).

SECTION

SECTION

Figure 5. Sections of Sargfabrik with spatial analysis, provided by BKK-3 architektur, self-derived (2024).

The interesting aspect to investigate further is how each CH opened itself to the public and provided public and semi-public spaces. In *Sargfabrik* the public spaces are highly institutionalised and rented out to external parties by the residents' association called *Verein für integrative Lebensgestaltung* (association for integrative living). This includes a kindergarten, the restaurant *Kant_ine VierZehn* and cultural event spaces in *Kulturshaus*. Moreover, the swimming area is accessible to non-residents as well to ensure affordability through additional generated income with membership fees or entry fees. A resident further described:

The swimming pool and sauna are open to the public and that is profitable. However, we also opened up other areas to external guests such as the cultural event rooms. This is how we became known to a broader audience in Vienna through *Kulturhaus* (Resident from Sargfabrik, April 22, 2024). (Figure 8)

The other complex, Gleis 21, dedicated its entire ground floor and parts of the cellar to uses for the neighbourhood and the general public. This decision was taken early in the design process (Architect from *einszueinsarchitektur*, interview, 6 May 2024). The music school *Klangwerk* is located downstairs. Furthermore, event and seminar spaces to rent are on the north-eastern end of the building. The spaces on the southern end are shared

Figure 6. Ground floor plans of Gleis 21 with spatial analysis, provided by einszueins architektur, adapted by the author (2024).

by the Café *Kaffeesatz* and another self-employed company. After two conversations with the barista, we concluded, that the Café is a crucial connection to the public. As they said:

We are happy to be here. Over time, we have established quite a robust clientele from the house, and the entire neighbourhood, but also some strangers come by because we are so

Figure 7. Ground floor plans of OASE.Inklusiv with spatial analysis, provided by einzueins architektur, self-derived (2024).

close to the train station. Thus, we will expand our Café space. (Barista from Gleis 21, April 20, 2024)

Ethnographic observations during our site visits revealed that the Café embodies the liveliness of everyday life in the CH to the outside world. It is a place where all residents and the wider neighbourhood meet. It is a meeting place that creates a sense of identity for Gleis 21 and a sense of belonging for its residents and visitors.

The question is always how the communal spaces are designed and organised. Usually, some are specifically discussed throughout the design process, whereas others are less determined in terms of use to enable flexible use and appropriation (Gruber 2021). One resident from *Gleis 21* argued:

We had different working groups in the design process and now also for everyday use. There is a working group for each room that feels responsible for it. In this way, we guarantee that not only the rooms are of the highest quality, but also the equipment. If a small thing doesn't work, such as a light bulb responsible group members replaced it. Ultimately, we manage everything ourselves and have no property management (Resident from Gleis 21, April 20, 2024). (Figure 9 and 10)

During a photo challenge, where one newcomer from *Gleis 21* participated, we learned how he uses the common spaces in his everyday life. The built environment encourages social bridging (Ager and Strang 2008) with other residents (Figure 11). The illustration

SARGFABRIK

Embedded in the Urban Fabric

Inner Courtyards

Restaurant

Exterior Staircases

Access Bridge

Swimming Pools

Cultural/Event Rooms

Exterior Corridors

Roof with Gardens

Maisonette Apartment

Groundfloor Gardens

Figure 8. Pictures of Sargfabrik with spatial analysis, self-derived (2024).

GLEIS 21

Community Kitchen

Library

Yoga Retreat Space

Indoor Playrooms

Sauna

Gym

Laundry Room

Bike Storage

Creative studio

Workshop

Creative Studio

Figure 9. Pictures of Gleis 21 with spatial analysis, self-derived (2024).

GLEIS 21

Figure 10. Pictures of Gleis 21 with spatial analysis, self-derived (2024).

Figure 11. Photochallenge with a newcomer in Gleis 21, self-derived (2024).

Figure 12. Pictures of OASE.Inklusiv with spatial analysis, self-derived (2024).

below shows the result of a photo challenge we conducted with a newcomer resident in *Gleis 21*. Over a period of one month (May, 2024), he took pictures of his everyday life at *Gleis 21*. He worked with different scales; the floor where his apartment is located, the whole complex and the outside appearance of the building embedded in the neighbourhood. At the end, we met to discuss his pictures and he shared, how he uses spaces in the buildings and how he experiences living in a collaborative community. The tasks and his comments highlight that he became an active member of the community. Through social bridging on corridors and intentional social activities in the communal spaces, he adds to the spirit of *solidary togetherness* and *everyday conviviality* (Amin 2010). We learned that the community life is enriching and supportive and generates a feeling of belonging for him (Anthias 2006; Yuval-Davis 2006).

The other collaborative housing project from *einszueinsarchitektur* – *OASE. inklusiv* – is much smaller and less oriented towards the neighbourhood. Still, we find it important to note, that the multi-purpose communal room on the ground floor is rentable for the public (Figure 12).

Participatory planning methods ensure the social production and appropriation of co-created spaces (Lefebvre 1992; de Certeau 1988; Soja 2019). The objective is to establish an adequate balance of individual and communal spaces (Architect from *einszueinsarchitektur*, interview, 6 May 2024). The design of the built environment enables everyday conviviality and social integration through interaction and encounters (Amin 2013). Communal spaces in the collaborative living model are also the ultimate reason for most residents to join the *Baugruppe*. The possibility of living in a solidarity community and experiencing everyday conviviality in contrast to the anonymity explored in most conventional residential buildings is the main driver:

I lived in so many *Altbauwohnungen* (Viennes city apartments) before. At some point, I just wanted to live in a building, where I have the opportunity to get to know my neighbours. I was fed up with the anonymity and CH is different in all aspects. But importantly we took design choices early on to enable us to meet every day intentionally or bump into each other. (Resident from Gleis 21, April 20, 2024)

Social housing between hostile and welcoming attitudes: the cases of Casa Bloc and Bellvitge in Barcelona

The Casa Bloc housing project in Barcelona, completed between 1933 and 1936, currently accommodates approximately 520 inhabitants. Initially, it was designed to improve the living conditions of workers by offering affordable yet high-quality architecture. Following a general refurbishment in 2012, the housing complex met contemporary living standards once again (Días and Llobet 2017). The architectural design was led by GATCPAC (Group of Catalan Architects and Technicians for the Progress of Contemporary Architecture), who adhered to modernist principles influenced by Le Corbusier. Access to dwellings is provided through long outdoor terraces located on the north and west sides of the building. The blocks themselves are elongated and narrow, featuring a two-bay metal structure. All apartments are duplexes, with living rooms and balconies on the lower floor and bedrooms on the upper floor (Pla, n.d.). Since 2015, Casa Bloc temporarily accommodates refugee families in one block, a measure initiated by the previous city council as part of the „Ciutat Refugi“ (Refugee City) initiative (UIC 2018).

The interviews that we conducted with residents in Casa Bloc reveal that a majority of residents are satisfied and content with their living arrangements in the complex. Most residents believe that the architectural design fosters a sense of community among tenants. They report being socially well-connected with their neighbours since they have been already living in Casa Bloc for decades. Therefore, we found that the *social cohesion* in the community is strong and built on bonding social capital (Putnam 2000).

However, when asked about the possibility of Casa Bloc welcoming refugee families (in addition to the reception centre already in place) and whether these families could easily integrate, opinions were divided due to varying attitudes towards the existing reception centre within the complex. Subsequent conversations with residents clarified that many of them hold negative perceptions of refugees, which makes them cautious about envisioning a more diverse community. As a resident told us:

I have never had a negative experience with an asylum seeker living here, but I heard stories about conflicts, theft, and drug-related issues affecting my neighbours - it's bad. (Resident Casa Bloc, May 1, 2023)

Others believed that there might not be enough capacity within the complex to accommodate refugee families. As another resident told us:

It is clear to me that Spanish citizens should be prioritized by the social housing system, before even considering foreigners. (Resident Casa Bloc, May 1, 2023)

This rather hostile narrative shows that by comparison to the Viennese models, the bridging social capital, which requires time and effort by residents to be formed, is almost non-existent (Korac 2003). The given everyday conviviality is characterised by anonymity and prejudicial fear of strangers and otherness (Purcell 2003). This significantly hinders the emergence of a diverse community (Amin 2010).

In our socio-spatial assessment of selected sites for their potential to welcome newcomers, we use our theoretical framework to show that housing (Ager and Strang 2008) has the power to create social bridges among diverse residents (Korac 2003). We determine architectural elements that facilitate neighbourly social encounters and community building. Two parks within the inner courtyard and the outer terraces are crucial locations where neighbours regularly meet, providing them with opportunities to take a break from their daily routines (Figure 13). Site visits to Casa Bloc revealed key places for social interactions, as depicted in Figure 14 (Figure 14). Our discussion with newly arrived refugees from Africa in Casa Bloc showed that these spaces are greatly valued for facilitating interaction both between refugees themselves and their surroundings. Nonetheless, they also told us that interactions with the other residents are so far almost non-existent.

Casa Bloc strikes a balance between common spaces that promote interaction and private spaces. Each apartment is equipped with a balcony on the opposite side, providing tenants with the option to retreat to their private areas when desired. Notably, one of the residents mentioned enjoying the open terraces during the night for stargazing. The architectural drawings, as shown in the initial drawings, incorporate a modern layout with designated areas for interaction highlighted in colour. These architectural features contribute to creating a communal atmosphere within Casa Bloc, fostering neighbourly interactions and providing spaces for relaxation and socialisation. However, the connected wings are presented in the model, with the southern wing isolated, housing the reception centre.

Nonetheless, the built environment, with its inner courtyards and exterior access corridors is designed to foster everyday conviviality (Amin 2010). For the diverse residents of Casa Bloc, overcoming the fear of strangers serves as a first step toward meaningful social interaction. This active process of community building and the development of social bridging requires time and the gradual resolution of racial prejudices (Korac 2003). Ultimately, such everyday conviviality can play a crucial role in fostering a sense of belonging and place-belongingness (Amin 2010; Yuval-Davis 2006; de Certeau 1988).

The other social housing complex where we conducted research was Bellvitge, situated in the neighbourhood of L'Hospitalet de Llobregat. It was developed during the 1960s using industrialised prefabricated construction techniques with reinforced

Figure 13. Drawings of Casa Bloc with spatial analysis, adapted and retrieved from <https://www.metalocus.es/en/news/inauguration-casa-bloc>.

concrete elements. During this period, a total of 77 buildings were constructed, providing accommodation for around 10.000 apartments. The Bellvitge project aimed to address the pressing housing needs of low-income families, many of whom had migrated from other regions of Spain to work in Barcelona's automotive industries. However, the initial development of Bellvitge was characterized by rapid construction without the inclusion of essential infrastructure, such as drainage and sewerage systems, social amenities, electricity, and paved roads. This situation led to collective protests organized by residents, who sought better living conditions. The rich history of successful activism continues to influence the level of resident participation and satisfaction in Bellvitge to this day. Today, the neighbourhood offers not only housing but also a rich social infrastructure including a library, restaurants, shops, educational facilities and offices (Bestraten Castells, Hormias Laperal, and Domínguez López 2015).

Our interview with residents' have indicated again that most residents are very content to live in Bellvitge. They believe that the architectural design of the complex is conducive to communal living, and most residents are well-acquainted with their neighbours. This evidences our imagined lived conviviality and a strong social

Figure 14. Pictures of Casa Bloc with spatial analysis, self-derived (2023).

cohesion (Amin 2013; Korac 2003). Furthermore and importantly, Bellvitge residents generally express a positive attitude towards potentially welcoming refugees into the complex, believing that newcomers can integrate smoothly since they generally see the complex as a diverse and welcoming environment. As one of the women we interviewed told us:

I have a migration background myself and I know many others here, who also have one. We are all part of the Bellvitge community now. (Resident Bellvitge, May 2, 2023)

Another woman suggested:

There are many vacant apartments currently. They could be used to host refugees. (Resident Bellvitge, May 2, 2023)

A refugee woman from a Sub-Saharan country who had been living in Bellvitge for four months shared her experiences upon arrival. She had previously resided in a Spanish reception centre where she experienced bad conditions and a complete lack of privacy. Later she stayed in a shared apartment outside Barcelona with six asylum seekers. Upon receiving full refugee status, she was responsible for finding work and housing without any financial (and other) support. She eventually found a room in Bellvitge where she pays a monthly rent that is rather expensive for her and had not yet established strong social bonds or connections with her neighbours. As she told us:

I don't know anyone except my roommates. It's hard, you know, life is hard. (Resident and Newcomer Bellvitge, May 2, 2023)

This shows that a diverse and inclusive community exists in Bellvitge. Given the areas' rich history in activism, the community has the potential to welcome newcomers and ensure a gradual process of community building and social integration (Korac 2003; Meissner and Heil 2021).

It is important to note that during our site visits to Bellvitge, we observed that it is a vibrant and active neighbourhood. Residents frequently utilize the green spaces, plazas, and social infrastructure. They gather in front of cafes and bars, take leisurely walks, use playgrounds, and often repurpose concrete plazas into makeshift football fields or event spaces. Additionally, Bellvitge features a traffic-calmed zone within the settlement, providing residents with enhanced safety, tranquillity, and improved air quality. The 'paseo', which functions as a Spanish 'La Rambla', is a main pedestrian street lined with smaller buildings used for various commercial purposes. The public areas offer residents opportunities to interact with their neighbours, providing a welcome break from their daily routines. Historical images illustrate the early development of Bellvitge, including the construction of the initial 'sleeping blocks', the presence of a campsite with an old chapel (Figure 15).

The built environment of Bellvitge is collectively and actively shaped by its residents. The management of the built environment is resident-led and embodies collective commoning (Kornberger and Borch 2015), referring to everyday appropriation and care of communal spaces. Through this active practice of commoning, the social production of space (Lefebvre 1992) converges with the pursuit of spatial justice (Soja 2019) enabling considerable flexibility in the use of communal spaces. In Bellvitge, the existing fabric of communal spaces is well-suited to foster social interaction with newcomers, thereby promoting social bridging (Ager and Strang 2008) and everyday conviviality (Amin 2010) (Figure 16).

Conclusion: imagining alternatives to conventional refugee housing

Our research in Vienna and Barcelona underscores the significant potential of collective housing models as realistic and affordable alternatives to the often substandard and precarious housing options available on the private market. Free-market housing, shaped by price fluctuations, speculation and gentrification dynamics, poses profound challenges to refugee integration. Building on existing scholarship in housing and refugee studies, our research highlights the critical role of adequate housing and social

Figure 15. Drawings and pictures of Bellvitge with spatial analysis, adapted from Bestraten Castells, Hormias Laperal, and Domínguez López (2015).

connections in supporting integration, particularly through the creation of social bridges, bonds and links (Ager and Strang 2008; Czischke and Huisman 2018).

Focusing on social housing in Barcelona and collaborative housing in Vienna, we found that these housing typologies can provide refugees with opportunities to connect with the host community while maintaining a balance between participation and privacy. In our examination of collective housing, we have observed that the smaller-scale housing projects in Vienna foster more active tenant communities, with a heightened interest in communal life and shared activities, while the larger-scale Bellvitge complex in Barcelona, with its history of activism, provides crucial social resources for community-building and social bridging.

However, mixed and diverse tenant communities bring challenges that warrant in-depth exploration and careful attention to minimise potential conflicts of conviviality (Amin 2010). This was particularly evident in Casa Bloc, where residents held diverse views on cohabitation with refugees. The limited availability and adequacy of social housing units also emerged as a key concern, as many regions grapple with limited resources and an insufficient number of affordable housing options. The allocation of these limited resources can become a contentious issue, with existing residents advocating for priority access to social housing, as seen in Casa Bloc. By contrast, Bellvitge's legacy of community radicalism has enhanced its capacity to integrate newcomers.

Promoting social cohesion in diverse housing communities is complex, as cultural, linguistic, and social differences can lead to tensions. Achieving social cohesion in

Figure 16. Pictures of Bellvitge with spatial analysis, self-derived (2023).

a diverse community (Korac 2003), as well as a sense of belonging (Anthias 2006; Yuval-Davis 2006) and place-belonging (Antonsich 2010; Lähdesmäki et al. 2016) necessitates intentional planning and dedicated community-building efforts. Grassroots organisations and refugee NGOs play pivotal roles in this process by organising community-building events and buddy and mentorship programmes that facilitate connections between the host community and newcomers. Yet, it is important to acknowledge that tenants may possess varying understandings of community due to differences in their cultural and socioeconomic backgrounds, resulting in distinct community needs. Consequently, collaborative housing may not suit every refugee family, but where successful, it offers a progressive and inclusive alternative to conventional refugee housing (Arroyo et al. 2021; Czischke and Huisman 2018), which is often marked by social and spatial segregation.

These collective housing models exemplify how space is created by social relations, echoing Lefebvre's theories on the production of space. We argue that space must be

intentionally designed to facilitate social relations in everyday life. Architectural elements—an often overlooked aspect in refugee integration literature (Delsante and Zambelli 2023)—hold significant potential to enhance community building (Korac 2003). Our socio-spatial analyses show that the selected housing sites are architecturally well-suited to foster inclusive communities that embody everyday conviviality (Amin 2010), integrating communal spaces and sites for spontaneous social encounters that enable the social (re)production of space (Lefebvre 1992), the appropriation and co-creation of the built environment (Gruber 2021; de Certeau 1988; Soja 2019) and the collective commoning of the entire site (Kornberger and Borch 2015).

Closing and shortening the stay in undignified reception centres and extending the support after refugee status is granted is of paramount importance for refugee integration. Regarding housing, governments should explore additional support measures in the housing search, including rent subsidies within social housing and collaborative housing complexes, as seen in Vienna's Sargfabrik, OASE.inklusiv and Gleis 21. Such measures have the potential to improve affordability for refugees who typically face severe financial constraints.

Expanding refugee access to the collective (social, cooperative and collaborative) housing sector is essential to build inclusive communities founded on mutual trust and solidarity rather than fear and prejudice. While addressing Europe's housing crisis requires deep structural and political change, it is crucial to envision new opportunities for vulnerable newcomers in the city. By recognising refugees' right to the city and enabling their active participation, this research advocates for meaningful transformations toward more inclusive and socially just urban living environments.

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